

Synthetic, spectral and antimicrobial studies of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) complexes of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones

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Abstract : The reactions of bis(cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride with semicarbazones/thiosemicarbazones derived by condensing semicarbazide hydrochloride/thiosemicarbazide with suitable ketones viz. 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 1-acetyl-2-naphthol and 2-acetyl-1-naphthol have been studied in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran and products of the type $[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ti}(\text{O} \overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{N}} \overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{X}})]$ have been isolated. Tentative structures have been proposed for these complexes based upon elemental analysis and spectral (electronic, IR, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR) data. In order to assess their growth inhibitory potency semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones and their titanium(IV) complexes were tested *in vitro* against some pathogenic fungi and bacteria. The results of these studies have been compared with the standard fungicide Micostatin and bactericide Streptomycin. The studies demonstrate that the ligands and their titanium(IV) complexes have comparable antimicrobial activity.

Keywords : Titanium(IV) complexes, semicarbazones, thiosemicarbazones, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones exhibit a wide variety of potentially useful biological properties^{1,2}. These are very important class of ligands obtained by condensation of semicarbazide hydrochloride or thiosemicarbazide with suitable aldehyde or ketones. They are very promising molecules in coordination chemistry because of their remarkable pharmacological properties such as antibacterial, antifungal, antitumor and antiparasitic activities³⁻⁸. The study of transition metal complexes of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones is of great interest due to their pharmacological activities which is frequently higher for the metal complexes than the free semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones⁹. On the other hand considerable importance has been attached to the chemistry of organic derivatives of titanium¹⁰. The synthesis and structure of titanocene complexes¹¹⁻¹⁵ have received much attention by virtue of their application as a catalyst in organic synthesis¹⁶, reductive fixation of small molecules¹⁷ and even as an agent with antitumor activity¹⁸ and antiproliferative activity¹⁹⁻²². Titanium marked tendency to form complexes of high coordination number has also stimulated interest in the study of their complexes with various ligands. Encouraged by these findings and our interest in the field of organotitanium complexes various semicarba-

zones, thiosemicarbazones and their corresponding titanium(IV) complexes have been prepared and characterized and their biological aspects have also been studied.

The ligands used in the present investigation are shown in Fig. 1. The ligands are semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones of 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 1-acetyl-2-naphthol and 2-acetyl-1-naphthol.

where X = O, semicarbazone; keto and enol form
X = S, thiosemicarbazone; thioketo and thiol form

Fig. 1. Tautomerism between keto/enol and thioketo/thiol form of the ligands in this work.

Experimental

Analytical methods and physical measurements : All the chemicals used in this work were of AR grade and solvents were dried by standard method. All reactions were carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions.

Nitrogen analysis has been carried out at CDRI on Elemental Analyzer Heraeus Vario EL III Carlo Erba 1108 and sulphur was determined by Messenger's method²³. The IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer using a model A-8400 S, Shimadzu using KBr pellets. The electronic spectra were taken with a Toshniwal spectrophotometer using distilled DMSO as a solvent. A Jeol AL 300 MHz spectrometer was used to obtain the ¹H spectra using DMSO-*d*₆ as a solvent. Titanium was estimated gravimetrically.

Molar conductance measurements were made in anhydrous dimethyl formamide at 36 ± 1 °C using a model 305 Systronics conductivity bridge. Molecular weight determinations were carried out by the Rast Camphor method²⁴.

General procedure for the synthesis of ligands :

Semicarbazones/thiosemicarbazones were synthesized by the condensation of suitable ketones viz. 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 1-acetyl-2-naphthol and 2-acetyl-1-naphthol with semicarbazide hydrochloride/thiosemicarbazide in 1 : 1 molar ratio using absolute alcohol as the reaction medium. The mixture was heated on a water bath for about an hour and then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The products were recrystallized from the same solvent and dried in vacuum. Based on the coordination sites available in the ligand system, they behave as bifunctional tridentate.

2-Hydroxypropiophenone semicarbazone (**1a**), light yellow solid, m.p. 185 °C; 2-hydroxypropiophenone thiosemicarbazone (**1b**), yellow crystals, m.p. 178 °C; 1-acetyl-2-naphthol semicarbazone (**1c**), brown solid, m.p. 108 °C; 1-acetyl-2-naphthol thiosemicarbazone (**1d**), light brown solid, m.p. 115 °C; 2-acetyl-1-naphthol semicarbazone (**1e**), yellow solid, m.p. 85 °C; 2-acetyl-1-naphthol thiosemicarbazone (**1f**), pale yellow solid, m.p. 90 °C.

General procedure for the synthesis of complexes :

To 2-hydroxypropiophenone semicarbazone (0.458 g, 2.5 mmol) or 2-hydroxypropiophenone thiosemicarbazone (0.495 g, 2.5 mmol) or 1-acetyl-2-naphtholsemicarbazone (0.610 g, 2.5 mmol) or 1-acetyl-2-naphtholthiosemicarbazone (0.648 g, 2.5 mmol) or 2-acetyl-1-naphtholsemicarbazone (0.610 g, 2.5 mmol), 2-acetyl-1-naphtholthiosemicarbazone (0.648 g, 2.5 mmol) in methanol-nitromethane mixture (40 ml, 50 : 50, v/v) was added

($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$)₂TiCl₂ (0.622 g, 2.5 mmol) in dry THF (40 ml) in the presence of stoichiometric amount of Et₃N (0.506 g, 5 mmol), and refluxed for 12–14 h at ~60 °C). Et₃N was used as HCl recovering agent. The precipitate of Et₃N.HCl was removed by filtration. After the complexation of the reaction the products were dried under reduced pressure and analysed. The purity of the compounds was checked by TLC using silica gel-G as an adsorbent.

[($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$)₂Ti(C₁₀H₁₁N₃O₂)] (**2a**) : Yield 84%; m.p. 205 °C; Calcd : N, 10.96; Ti, 12.49 (%), Found : C, 10.90; Ti, 12.42 (%), Mol. Wt. Calcd. : 383.30 g, Found : 375 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 1600 (C=N), 603, 592 (Ti-O), 520, 480 (Ti-N), 358 (Ti-S); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 6.45 (s), 7.00–7.60 (m).

[($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$)₂Ti(C₁₀H₁₁N₃OS)] (**2b**) : Yield 82%; m.p. 180 °C (d); Calcd : N, 10.50; S, 8.01; Ti, 11.97 (%), Found : C, 10.42; S, 8.00; Ti, 11.87 (%), Mol. Wt. Calcd. : 399.88 g, Found : 391 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 1630 (C=N), 610, 600 (Ti-O), 527, 538 (Ti-N), 355 (Ti-S); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 6.38 (s), 7.10–7.60 (m).

[($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$)₂Ti(C₁₃H₁₁N₃O₂)] (**2c**) : Yield 86%; m.p. 158 °C (d); Calcd : N, 10.00; Ti, 11.40 (%). Found : C, 9.79; Ti, 11.32 (%), Mol. Wt. Calcd : 419.84 g, Found : 409 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 1610 (C=N); 610, 595 (Ti-O), 523, 609 (Ti-N), 362 (Ti-S); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 6.35 (s) 7.15–7.70 (m).

[($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$)₂Ti(C₁₃H₁₁N₃OS)] (**2d**) : Yield 88%; m.p. 155 °C (d); Calcd : N, 9.63; S, 7.35; Ti, 10.98 (%), Found : C, 9.52; S, 7.25; Ti, 10.90 (%). Mol. Wt. Calcd. : 435.91 g; Found : 429 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 1600 (C=N), 523, 590 (Ti-O), 540, 430 (Ti-N), 365 (Ti-S); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 6.44 (s), 7.10–7.60 (m).

[($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$)₂Ti(C₁₃H₁₁N₃O₂)] (**2e**) : Yield 91%; m.p. 156 °C (d); Calcd. : N, 10.00; Ti, 11.40 (%), Found : C, 9.75; Ti, 1.32 (%), Mol. Wt. Calcd : 419.84 g, Found : 402 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 1590 (C=N), 532, 429 (Ti-O), 525, 520 (Ti-N), 370 (Ti-S); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 6.40 (s) 7.00–7.50 (m).

[($\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$)₂Ti(C₁₃H₁₁N₃OS)] (**2f**) : Yield 89%; m.p. 148 °C (d); Calcd : N, 9.63; S, 7.35; Ti, 10.98(%), Found : C, 9.51; S, 7.25; Ti, 10.92 (%), Mol. Wt. Calcd. : 435.91 g; Found : 425 g; FT-IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) ν : 1600 (C=N), 540, 430 (Ti-O), 532, 429 (Ti-N), 369 (Ti-S); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ : 6.38 (s), 7.15–7.70 (w).

Antibacterial and antifungal test :

In vitro antifungal activities of the ligands and their complexes were tested using the radial growth method at a concentration of 100 and 200 ppm. Micostatin was used as reference compound for antifungal activities. Antibacterial activities of the ligands and the complexes were tested using the paper disc diffusion method²⁵⁻²⁷ at a concentration of 500 and 1000 ppm. Streptomycin was used as reference compound for antibacterial activities. The test organisms used in these investigations are *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (bacteria) and *A. flavus*, *F. oxysporum*, *R. phaseoli* (fungi).

Results and discussion

Bis(η^5 -cyclopentadienyl)titanium(IV) dichloride, (η^5 -C₅H₅)₂TiCl₂ reacts with a bifunctional tridentate semicarbazone/thiosemicarbazone in 1 : 1 molar ratio to form complexes of the type [(η^5 -C₅H₅)₂Ti(O[∘]N[∘]X)].

All the newly synthesized titanium complexes are orange-brown crystals, stable to ~200 °C, undergoing decomposition above this temperature and soluble in most common organic solvents viz. THF, acetone, chloroform, dichloromethane. The complexation reaction are accompanied by proton loss from the ligand and on the basis of spectral studies, elemental analysis and molecular weight determination, the following structure is assigned to [(η^5 -C₅H₅)₂Ti(O[∘]N[∘]X)] complexes (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Proposed structure of [(η^5 -C₅H₅)₂Ti(O[∘]N[∘]X)] complexes.

The assigned structure is analogous to the reported Schiff base complexes of tin, titanium and zirconium²⁸. Titanium has a coordination number of five in these complexes which is according to the reported studies^{29,30}.

It was observed earlier that the reactions of such ligands with different metal salts under varied reaction condi-

tions yielded complexes of the corresponding enol or thiol form of the ligand where it functions as dibasic tridentate fashion bonding through O, N and X (X = O or S in enol or thiol form) atoms with different metal ions. Neutral and bidentate behaviour was also encountered in certain cases with bonding through X (X = O or S) and azomethine N. However, in the present study the ligand uniformly act as dibasic tridentate bonding through X (X = O or S in enol and thiol form respectively after deprotonation), azomethine N and phenolic O (after deprotonation).

Electrical conductance measurements in nitrobenzene show these complexes to be non-electrolytes and to be susceptible to hydrolysis. From molecular weight determination it is concluded that they are monomeric species.

Electronic spectra :

Two intense maxima were observed in the ligands at 250 nm and 315 nm. These bands are fully consistent with the typical spectrum of semicarbazones and thiosemicarbazones (cyclic form) and may be attributed to the ϕ - ϕ^* and π - π^* benzenoid transitions. In the corresponding 1 : 1 titanium complexes (Fig. 1) an additional band at around 402–412 nm is observed which may be assigned to the charge transfer band^{31,32} according to ($n - 1$) $d^0 ns^0$ electronic configuration of titanium(IV). The complexes are all diamagnetic.

IR spectra :

Absorption bands indicating the presence of the cyclopentadienyl groups are found at 3100 ν (C-H), 1450 ν (C-C), 1015 ν (C-H) in-plane and 810 cm^{-1} ν (C-H) out-of-plane. Appearance of these cyclopentadienyl ring bands in the Schiff base derivatives indicate that electrons in these groups remain delocalized and π -bonded (η^5) to the metal³³. Apart from this, the band at 440 cm^{-1} may be assigned to ν ((Ti-C₅H₅))³⁴ vibrations.

The uncomplexed ligands shows bands assignable to ν (NH) in the region 3200–2900 cm^{-1} . But the ν (OH) band at 3500 cm^{-1} is not observed and this may be due to strong hydrogen bonding, which probably shifts ν (OH) to lower frequency. The bands due to ν (OH) disappeared in all the complexes indicating coordination of phenolic oxygen atom after deprotonation.

The C=N stretching vibration of the free ligand occurs^{35,36} at 1630 cm^{-1} but on complexation this band, in

all the cases, is shifted to lower frequency suggesting that the ligand is coordinated to the metal via the azomethine nitrogen atom³⁷. This lowering of C=N bond order as a result of M-N bond formation³⁸ is evident from the appearance of new $\nu(\text{M-N})$ bands in the far infrared region.

It is evident that in the present complexes both the phenolic OH and C=X (X = O or S) disappeared and new bands at 1050 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C-O})$ and $720\text{--}700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C-S})$ is observed suggesting coordination of metal ion through thiole-sulphur and phenolic oxygen via deprotonation. Moreover, a new $\nu(\text{C=N})$ stretching mode is also lowered by about 25 cm^{-1} . It may, therefore be

inferred that in the present complexes the ligands is dibasic, tridentate, bonding through O, N and S atoms.

Bands in the region $570\text{--}540$, $525\text{--}425$ and $355\text{--}370\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to $\nu(\text{Ti-O})$, $\nu(\text{Ti-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Ti-S})$ respectively³⁹⁻⁴¹.

¹H NMR spectra :

The broad signal at $\delta\ 6.5\text{ ppm}$ and $\delta\ 7.9\text{ ppm}$ may be assigned to the phenyl resonance region. The NH proton ($\delta\ 10.10\text{ ppm}$) signals in the spectra of ligands completely disappeared in the all complexes suggesting dibasic tridentate NXO (X = O or S) donor nature of the ligand. Also absence of phenolic proton signals in the complexes indicates removal of it and supports the bond formation to metal through oxygen. In addition, signals for $\pi\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$ appeared at $\delta\ 6.5$ (slightly broadened singlet).

Antimicrobial results :

All the titanium(IV) coordination compounds were tested against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The result shows that all the complexes were active against Gram-positive bacteria while less active against *E. coli*, which is Gram-negative. The result further show that complexes were more active the Schiff bases⁴² which indicates that metallation increases the activity.

In vitro antibacterial activity of the ligands and the complexes were tested using the paper disc diffusion method at a concentration of 1 mg/disc . Streptomycin was used as reference compounds for antibacterial activity. The data have been recorded in Table 1. The antifungal activity of some ligands and their corresponding titanium complexes are screened *in vitro* against *Aspergillus flavus*, *Fusarium oxysporum* etc. For antifungal activity,

Table 1. Antibacterial screening data of the ligands and their titanium(IV) complexes

Compd.	Diameter of inhibition zone (mm)			
	(conc. in ppm)			
	<i>Escherichia coli</i> (-)		<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (+)	
	500	1000	500	1000
	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
L ¹ H ₂	8	10	11	16
L ² H ₂	8	11	12	18
L ³ H ₂	7	10	12	16
L ⁴ H ₂	9	12	13	15
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiL}^1]$	10	13	15	19
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiL}^2]$	14	16	17	19
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiL}^3]$	8	12	18	18
$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiL}^4]$	11	16	16	17
Streptomycin	15	17	14	17

L¹H₂ = (C₁₀H₁₃N₃O₂); L²H₂ = (C₁₀H₁₃N₃OS);
L³H₂ = (C₁₃H₁₃N₃O₂); L⁴H₂ = (C₁₃H₁₃N₃OS)

Table 2. Antifungal activity of the ligands and their titanium(IV) complexes

Micro organisms		L ² H ₂		$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiL}^2]$		L ³ H ₂		$[(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{TiL}^3]$	
		100	200	100	200	100	200	100	200
		ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
<i>A. flavus</i>	IZ	24	37	14	25	13	24	21	29
	(AI)	(0.81)	(0.79)	(0.69)	(1.20)	(0.53)	(1.10)	(0.76)	(1.00)
<i>F. oxysporum</i>	IZ	23	37	19	18	14	21	15	17
	(AI)	(0.80)	(0.90)	(0.82)	(0.43)	(0.54)	(1.25)	(0.72)	(0.69)
<i>R. phaseoli</i>	IZ	22	35	16	27	25	31	25	38
	(AI)	(1.00)	(1.54)	(0.82)	(0.91)	(1.00)	(1.54)	(1.18)	(1.63)

IZ = Inhibition zone (diameter in mm); AI = Activity index (inhibition zone of test compounds/inhibition zone of standard).

L²H₂ = (C₁₀H₁₃N₃OS); L³H₂ = (C₁₃H₁₃N₃O₂); L⁵H₂ = (C₁₃H₁₃N₃OS).

radial growth method was used. Micostatin was used as reference compound. The data have been recorded in Table 2. All the complexes showed high activity against some pathogenic fungi even at lower concentrations and the inhibition of fungal growth was found to be dependent on the concentration of the compounds.

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